

Appendix 5.1: List of reviewed vision studies

Synthesis table of reviewed visions. Columns refer to activity sector, main actors involved in vision development, year of vision, main goals (PS: policy support, BS: business support, QoL: quality of life), elements in vision (Nature, NCP: nature's contributions to people, QoL-NCP: QoL supported by NCP, QoL-other: QoL supported by other factors (e.g. jobs, education)). Open dots indicate that the vision only refers to the environment in general, B and E indicate that the vision only refers to biodiversity and ecosystem services respectively; NCP categories: M – material, R – regulating, NM – non-material.

Sector	Actors	Year	Spatial scope	Main goals			Elements in vision				References
				PS	BS	QoL	Nature	NCP	QoL-NCP	QoL-other	
Cross-sector	Academic	2040	Western Europe	•			B	M,R,NM			(Pérez-Soba, M., Paterson, J., Metzger, 2015)
Cross-sector	Academic	2050	Europe	•		•	o				(Mont, Neuvonen, & Lähteenoja, 2014)
Cross-sector	Academic	2050	Europe	•		•	•	M,R,NM	•		(Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency & Stockholm Resilience Centre, 2009)
Agriculture	Int.Org.	2030	Europe	•	•		•	M,R,NM	•		(Food Drink Europe, 2012)
Agriculture	Int.Org.	2030	Europe	•	•	•	•	M,R,NM	•		(Barabanova, Zanolli, Schlüter, & Stopes, 2015)
Agriculture	Int.Org.	2030	Europe	•			o	M		•	(Maggio, van Criekinge, & Malingreau, 2015)
Energy	Int.Org.	2030	Europe	•	•		o				(EC, 2006)
Fisheries	Int.Org.	2030	Europe	•	•		E	M		•	(EATIP, 2012)
Forestry	Int.Org.	2020 ¹	Europe	•	•		•	M,R,NM	•	•	(Forest Europe, 2011)
Forestry	Int.Org.	2030	Europe	•	•		•	M,R,NM			(The Forest-based Sector ETP, 2013)
Cross-sector	Int.Org.	2030	Europe	•	•		o	M		•	(BECOTEPS, 2011)
Environ.	NGO	2023 ¹	Europe	•			•	M,R,NM	•		(Sylvén & Widstrand, 2013)
Agriculture	Academic	2030	Western Europe	•	•		o	M,NM	•	•	(McKee & Holstead, 2014)
Environ.	Int.Org.	2030	Europe	•		•	•	M,R,NM	•	•	(UNEP/UNECE, 2016)
Environ.	Int.Org.	2050	Europe	•		•	•	M,R,NM	•		(EC, 2011)
Forestry	Academic	2050	Sweden ¹	•	•	•	•	M,R,NM	•	•	(Sandström et al., 2016)
Cross-sector	National Org.	2030	France ¹	•			•	M,R,NM	•	•	(Commissariat Général au Développement Durable, 2013)
Agriculture	National Org.	2025	France ¹	•			•	M,R,NM			(Ministère de l'Écologie et du Développement Durable, 2005)
NBSAP	Government	2020	Georgia ³	•			•	M,R,NM	•		(Ministry of Environment and Natural Resources Protection of Georgia, 2014)
NBSAP	Government	2024	Kyrgyzstan	•			•	M,R	•	•	(Ministry of Environmental Protection of Kyrgyzstan, 1998)
NBSAP	Government	Open	Turkmenistan	•			•	M,R,NM	•	•	(Ministry of Nature Protection of Turkmenistan, 2002)
NBSAP	Government	2020	Armenia	•		•	•	M,R,NM	•	•	(Ministry for Nature Protection of Armenia, 1999)

NBSAP	Government	2020	Russia	•		•	•	M,R	•	•	(Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment of the Russian Federation, 2014)
NBSAP	Government	2020	Belarus ^{2,3}	•			•	M,R	•		(Council of Ministers of the Republic of Belarus, 2015a)
NBSAP	Government	2020	Azerbaijan ²	•			•	M,R	•		(President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2017)
NBSAP	Government	2020	Tajikistan	•	•	•	•	M,R, NM	•	•	(National Centre for Biodiversity and Biosecurity of the Republic of Tajikistan, 2016)
NBSAP	Government	2020	Moldova	•		•	•	M,R	•	•	(Government of the Republic of Moldova, 2015)
NBSAP	Government	2020	Ukraine ^{2,3}	•		•	•	M,R, NM	•	•	(Parliament of Ukraine, 2016)
NBSAP	Government	2030	Belarus								(Council of Ministers of the Republic of Belarus, 2015a)
Cross-sector	Government	2050	Kazakhstan	•			•	M,R	•	•	(President of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 2012)
Cross-sector	Government	2050	Uzbekistan	•	•	•	•	M,R, NM	•	•	(State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Nature Protection, 2012)
Cross-sector	Government	2030	Russia	•			•	M	•	•	(Ministry of Economic Development of the Russian Federation, 2013)
Cross-sector	Government	2030	Belarus	•	•	•	•	M,R, NM	•	•	(Council of Ministers of the Republic of Belarus, 2015b)
Cross-sector	Academic	2020	Global			•	•	M,R, NM	•	•	(Kates & Clark, 1999)
Cross-sector	Academic	2050	Global			•	•	M,R, NM	•	•	(IGBP, 2009)
Cross-sector	Academic	2050	Global	•		•	•	M,R	•	•	(UNEP, 2012)
Cross-sector	Private	2050	Global	•	•		•	M,R	•	•	(WBCSD, 2010)
Cross-sector	Academic	2050	Global	•		•	•	M		•	(WBGU, 2011)
Cross-sector	NGO	2025	Global	•	•	•	•	M,R, NM	•		(Wetlands International, 2015)
Cross-sector	Int.Org.	2024	Global	•	•	•	•	M,R, NM	•		(Ramsar Convention Secretariat, 2016)
Agriculture	Int.Org.	2050	Global	•			•	M,R	•	•	(FAO, 2014)
Agriculture	Int.Org.	2050	Global	•			•	M			(FAO, 2009)
Agriculture	Multiple	2050	Global	•	•		○	M,R	•	•	(WEF, 2010, 2012)
Environ.-Climate	NGO	2050	Global	•			•	M,R	•	•	(Greenpeace, 2009)
Energy	Multiple	2030	Global	•		•	○	M	•	•	(Ki-moon, 2011; WB, 2012)
Energy	Multiple	2050	Global	•				M	•	•	(WWF/Ecofys/OMA, 2011)
Energy	NGO	2050	Global	•			○	M	•	•	(Olesen, Kvetny, & la Rovere, 2002)
Energy	Int. Org.	2050	Global	•			○	M	•	•	(IPCC, 2012)
Energy	Academic	2050	Global	•		•	•	M			(van Vuuren et al., 2012)
Fisheries	Multiple	2030	Global		•		○	M			(CASS, 2008)
Transport	Private	2040	Global		•					•	(SSI, 2014)
Water	Multiple	2030	Global	•			○	M			(FAO, 2015)
Environ.-Water	Multiple	2050	Global	•			•	M,R, NM	•	•	(United Nations World Water Assessment Programme, 2015)
Environ.-Water	Multiple	2025	Global	•		•	•	M,R	•	•	(Cosgrove & Rijsberman, 2014)

Environ.- Water	NGO	2020 ¹	Global							•	(WaterAid, 2013)
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- 1- Visions with a national scope or a short-term frame (<15 years) that were included in the regional review for their thematic contribution to the sectoral analyses
- 2- NBSAPs from Eastern Europe and Central Asia included in Figure 5.3
- 3- NBSAPs from Eastern Europe and Central Asia included in Figure 5.4

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